

B Expert Evaluation Questionnaire

Design principles for responsible privacy heuristics - an evaluation questionnaire

This questionnaire is part of a Master's thesis titled *"An Approach for Designing Responsible Privacy Heuristics"*.

Context: Privacy compliance is a major concern for legal entities handling Personal Information (PI), as noncompliance leads to substantial fines. Regulations require these entities to implement privacy protection mechanisms (privacy solutions) and inform data subjects (DSs) about PI processing. However, DSs often struggle to understand relevant information and effectively use these mechanisms, leaving their privacy vulnerable. Privacy heuristics offer a potential solution by assisting users in making informed decisions. Yet, their design is complex, prone to bias, and, if done irresponsibly, may lead to unethical or manipulative outcomes. This research aims to address these challenges by developing an approach that offers design principles to guide the design and development of Responsible Privacy Heuristics (RPHs) for usable privacy-aware systems or solutions. These design principles have been formulated based on best practices in the responsible and ethical design area, taking into consideration available fair design patterns and trying our best to avoid the dark design patterns.

These design principles are intended to enhance traditional usability privacy heuristics, transforming them into RPHs. The acceptance criteria serve as a tool to assess whether a design resulting from an RPH correctly applies the principle.

The principles and their acceptance criteria (AC) are presented in Table 1. Given your experience, we seek your input to evaluate the **clarity** and **applicability** of these design principles, as well as the **validity** of their associated AC. We define these criteria as follows:

DP - Q1. Clarity: How easy is it to understand what this design principle is recommending from a design perspective?

1. Very difficult 2. Difficult 3. Neutral 4. Easy 5. Very easy

DP - Q2. Applicability: Can this principle be realistically applied in real-world design scenarios?

1. Not at all 2. Not very applicable 3. Neutral 4. Somehow applicable 5. Applicable

DPAC - Q3. Validity: Can this AC be applied, tested, and verified objectively by involved stakeholders (e.g., developers, testers) without ambiguity?

1. Not at all 2. Not sufficiently valid 3. Neutral 4. Somehow valid 5. Valid

Please evaluate each Design Principle (DP) and its related Acceptance Criteria (AC) by filling in the table below. Use the 1 to 5 scales provided in the questions above. You may use the Comments row to offer suggestions, note strengths or limitations, or share any relevant insights based on your expertise.

Table 1. Design principles and their acceptance criteria for responsible privacy heuristics

<p>DP1. Neutral: A RPH should present information about privacy choices in a neutral and balanced manner, avoiding framing that could lead to biased or skewed decisions.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP1AC1. Are all choices presented with equal prominence? (i.e., Are they displayed in a way to allow users to perceive them as equally relevant?)</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP1 or DP1AC1</p>		
<p>DP2. Honesty and Clarity: A RPH should ensure that all information presented to users is truthful, clear, and easy to understand.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP2AC1. Is the privacy-related choice or information presented accurately and comprehensibly to users of different levels of expertise?</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP2 or DP2AC1</p>		
<p>DP3. Navigable and actionable privacy: A RPH should help users easily identify, understand, and act upon privacy-related information.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP3AC1. Is the path to privacy-related mechanisms easy to learn and intuitive to use?</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>DP3AC2. Are actionable privacy mechanisms (e.g., privacy settings) easily recognizable and intuitive to use?</p>	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP3, DP3AC1, or DP3AC2</p>		
<p>DP4. Pressure-free: A RPH should not impose time constraints, emotional manipulation, or other coercive tactics that pressure users into making privacy decisions.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1

<p>DP4AC1. Are users free to make privacy decisions without being subject to: time constraints; exclusive time-limited offers or other alleged financial gains in exchange for PI; coercive tactics exploiting emotional and social factors (e.g., guilt shaming, fear of missing out, and bandwagon effect)?</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP4 or DP4AC1</p>		
<p>DP5. Benefit-risk balance: A RPH should highlight user benefits and proactively minimize potential privacy risks.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP5AC1. Are the benefits and potential privacy risks associated with a given action clearly communicated?</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP5 or DP5AC1</p>		
<p>DP6. Consequences awareness: A RPH should provide feedback related to privacy choices, avoiding obscuring consequences, which could affect the users' decision-making.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP6AC1. Are the consequences of privacy choices clearly communicated to the user during or after a decision-making process, through real-time feedback or confirmation?</p>	Q3	
	1	
<p>DP6AC2. Is information about the implications of users' privacy choices easy to find?</p>	1	
<p>Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP6, DP6AC1 or DP6AC2</p>		
<p>DP7. Empowering: A RPH should support users to select privacy choices that align with their privacy requirements.</p>	Q1	Q2
	1	1
<p>DP7AC1. Does the privacy solution provide intuitive and customizable privacy options that enable users to control, correct, and retract their privacy choices in a way that aligns with their preferences and requirements?</p>	Q3	
	1	

Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP7 or DP7AC1		
DP8. Context-aware: A RPH should help users assess privacy decisions in context, considering factors such as data sensitivity, purpose of collection and use, recipient identity, and potential risks.	Q1	Q2
	1	1
DP8AC1. Does the privacy solution provide users with context-specific information that allows them to assess the sensitivity and risks implied by the type of data being requested (e.g., health, financial, or personal data), the purpose for its use, and the identity of the recipients?	Q3	
	1	
Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP8 or DP8AC1		
DP9. Situation-aware: A RPH should adapt to different situations to provide relevant, meaningful, and actionable guidance.	Q1	Q2
	1	1
DP9AC1. Is privacy guidance provided based on the user’s current situation (e.g., location, device type, or task being performed) and interaction context (e.g., signing up for a service vs. sharing a photo)?	Q3	
	1	
Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP9 or DP9AC1		
DP10: Accessible and inclusive: A RPH should ensure that users, regardless of their abilities or technical expertise, can understand and act upon privacy-related information.	Q1	Q2
	1	1
DP10AC1. Is privacy-related information provided in multiple formats (e.g., simple language, assistive technologies, alternative formats) to accommodate users' varying preferences, expertise, sensory needs, and disabilities?	Q3	
	1	
Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP10 or DP10AC1		
DP11. Regulation Compliant: A RPH must not encourage or lead to violating privacy legislation (e.g., purpose limitation, data minimization).	Q1	Q2
	1	1

DP11AC1. Are privacy-related choices and information compliant with the relevant privacy legislation (e.g., GDPR in Europe)?	Q3
Please use this space if you have any suggestions to improve or extend DP11 or DP11AC1	1

Q4. Completeness: Do the current design principles, collectively, cover necessary aspects of responsible privacy? Are they adaptable across different privacy contexts (e.g., social media, online banking, healthcare) and mechanisms (e.g., privacy settings and policies)?

Please use this space to answer Q4. Feel free to point out gaps and make suggestions.

Final Feedback: If you have any additional comments, suggestions, or concerns about this approach that were not covered in the previous questions, please share them here.

Please use this space for the final feedback.

Thank you for participating!
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